

POSSIBILITIES AND DISADVANTAGES OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Currently, one of the priority innovative technologies implemented in the continuous education system is the use of the possibilities of the virtual educational environment in the modern training system. In this article, the opportunities and shortcomings of distance education in the development of informational competence of teachers in the field of virtual technologies are discussed in detail.*

Keywords: *modularity, mobility, comprehensiveness, technology-based, social equality, internationalization, changing the role of the teacher.*

Recently, the concept of distance education has entered the educational system, and its implementation is gaining mass. The analysis of many methodological sources shows that the implementation of distance education can help to overcome the difficulties associated with the formation and improvement of the awareness of teachers about virtual technologies.

For the reality of our country, distance education is a relatively new phenomenon, which is distinguished by different definitions, concepts, forms, methods and approaches [1].

Many local and foreign specialists are working in the field of distance education theory and practice, their scientific research helps the development of distance education and its introduction into the educational process [2]. Among them: A.A.Andreev, A.A.Akkhayan, A.I.Bershinsky, A.A.Verbitsky, N.A. Gavrilov, M.P.Karpenko, E.S.Komrakov, M.I.Nezhurina, D.P.Okolelov, E.S. Polat, A.M.Romanov, V.I.Soldatkin, A.G.Teslinov, V.P.Tikhromirov, A.V. Khutorskoy, S.A.Shchennikov and others. However, despite many years of experience in the theory and practice of distance education, there is no generally accepted definition, a uniform understanding of the main terms of distance education, which leads to uncertainty in the interpretation of the same phenomenon and information leads to inconsistency of perception. Therefore, it is important to analyze the existing definitions of distance education [3].

Distance learning in various sources is based on the student's independent learning, as a new form of organizing the educational process; used personal computers, video and audio, space and optical fiber technologies as a set of information technologies that ensure the delivery of the main volume of the studied material to the student, interactive interaction of students and teachers in the educational process is considered as a new level of extramural education that provides the use of information technologies [4].

Although there are different opinions on distance education, most distance education researchers emphasize the following:

- modularity - the content of distance learning is expressed in modules, which allows students to create an individual learning trajectory according to their educational needs;

- mobility - it is understood that feedback is established between the teacher and the learner;
- comprehensiveness - providing education to many students at the same time;
- technology-based - use of new information and communication technologies in the educational process;

- social equality - students have equal opportunities for education, regardless of their place of residence, health, and financial situation;

- internationality - the existence of mutual exchange of educational achievements in the world community to achieve educational goals;

- changing the role of the teacher - coordinating the process of acquiring knowledge [3], correcting the current course, giving advice when creating an individual curriculum, managing educational projects tasks are assigned. He leads mutual support study groups, helps students to determine their professional destiny. In the distance education system, the asynchronous interaction of the students and the teacher usually includes the exchange of messages by sending them to the addresses of the correspondents. This allows to analyze incoming information and respond to reporters at a convenient time. Asynchronous methods of interaction are e-mail or electronic computer networks;

- specialized monitoring of the quality of education - in the distance education system, final monitoring, interviews, practical training, project and design work, externship, computerized intellectual testing systems are used as forms of monitoring [1] . It should be noted that controlling the quality of distance education, solving the problem of its compliance with educational standards is important for the success of the entire educational system.

Thus, the goal-oriented and controlled independent activity of the student forms the basis of the distance learning educational process. In this case, the student can communicate with the teacher by telephone, fax, e-mail or regular mail, as well as face-to-face, in a place convenient for him, according to an individual schedule, with a set of special study guides and a teacher. he can get knowledge if he has the opportunity.

In the implementation of distance education, the achievements are made transparent, that is, providing everyone with the opportunity to receive education; such as the ability to use educational programs at different levels.

Obviously, distance learning, like any other form of education, has several disadvantages, and they are:

- the possibilities of social interaction through computer networks do not reach the same level of quality of communication as during the direct communication of participants in the educational process;

- anonymity of educational institutions;

- the impossibility of standardizing the content of education;

- insufficiently developed criteria for evaluating virtual works;

- additional costs for communication services;

- the population's pessimistic attitude towards computer and telecommunication means;

- increasing demand for technical skills of students and teachers [5].

Because of this, distance education is aimed primarily at adults who do not have the opportunity to attend training in educational institutions, but who have practical motivation and need to improve their skills.

In the traditional additional vocational education system, students acquire knowledge without concrete contact with practice. Distance learning implies the acquisition of such knowledge and skills by adults, which are necessarily and immediately applied in practical activities [6].

Distance learning as a technology is defined as follows: distance education technologies are educational technologies that are implemented mainly using information and telecommunication technologies during direct or partially indirect interaction between the student and the teacher. understood. We do not agree with this opinion, because distance education cannot be a technology, because its teaching system uses both information and communication technologies and pedagogical technologies. At the same time, the use of the term distance technologies equates information, communication and pedagogical technologies, which can be used in any other form of education [3].

Distance learning allows optimization of information, communication and educational technologies. The combination of these technologies ensures the quality of the learning process that students expect, because the weakness of any technology makes the learning process lose the power it needs to meet the complex learning needs of students [5].

According to many pedagogues conducting research in the field of distance education, the disadvantages of introducing distance education into the system of professional development of pedagogical staff include:

- reducing the potential audience of teachers, which is explained by the lack of technical possibility to join the educational process (computer, Internet connection);
- making it mandatory to pass computer training as a prerequisite for entering the distance education system;
- lack of adaptation of educational-methodical complexes to distance learning courses;
- insufficiently developed systems of administrative management of the educational process in the distance mode and a decrease in the quality of distance education compared to full-time study [7].

Thus, in order to increase the knowledge of teachers in the field of ICT for the organization of distance education in the advanced education system, it is necessary to solve a number of problems that prevent the introduction of a new form for teachers.

Remote implementation of teacher retraining and professional development courses has its own characteristics. If we pay attention to the implementation of distance education, teachers should not only improve their professional skills in a distance form, but also be ready to use this form of education in pedagogical practice.

At the same time, the uniqueness of the subject, learning goals, not only the content of distance education, its structure, but also the chosen educational model.

In addition, “pedagogical staff at various stages of distance education in advanced educational institutions (development of the training course, verification of educational tasks, counseling, etc.) the absence of it creates a negative attitude to the new form of teaching”. Therefore, in order to introduce distance education into the teacher training system, it is necessary to develop normative documents that regulate and encourage the activities of teachers of the additional pedagogical education system in the field of distance education [8].

Favorable conditions are being created for the use of distance education in retraining and professional development of teachers, as most schools in our country, as well as educational

institutions engaged in training and professional development of teachers, have classrooms equipped with the necessary computer equipment [1]. Every year, many teachers realize the need for remote training, and distance courses are organized in them.

In order to generalize the experience of using distance education in the advanced education system, to identify common difficulties and mistakes in the use of distance education, we researched distance education courses designed for teaching staff [9]. The results of the study of Internet resources, distance education courses for teachers, as well as the analysis of the activities of distance education centers allowed us to identify errors and complications in the use of the distance form of education in the advanced education system [1].

We consider it important to create a single informational and educational space for the advanced education system. Because one of the main advantages of distance education is distance openness. Creating such a space allows teachers to take a distance learning course [3] not only in the regional training institute, but also in the training system.

Currently, there are no distance education courses for teachers in a specific subject area, using virtual technology tools, dedicated to the actual issues of the methodology of passing the subject. Therefore, questions related to methodological training and professional development of teachers in the field of virtual technologies are still open [1].

Many distance learning courses are self-directed and do not involve interaction between instructors and learners. The weakest link is the lack of necessary equipment and technologies for the implementation of distance education, on the basis of which educational centers cannot properly evaluate their capabilities.

We believe that distance education has a huge potential to improve the knowledge of teachers on virtual technologies. Currently, there is an order for an advanced education system for educational services in the field of virtual technologies, which, in our opinion, could be organized most effectively through distance learning. The main directions of distance education of teachers in order to improve their knowledge in the field of virtual technologies include:

- supporting the activity of the teacher on the use of virtual technologies in the educational process;
- development of innovative educational programs, models of integration of virtual technologies into the educational process;
- organization of activities to create collective creative projects regarding the use of virtual technologies in the educational process;
- conducting educational consultations for teachers within the content of educational programs, etc.

Thus, the analysis of many pedagogical studies devoted to the problems of using distance education [3] in the system of retraining and professional development of teachers shows the use of this form of education to increase the knowledge of teachers in virtual technologies. made it possible to identify the main advantages: creative, critical thinking skills are formed in teachers during learning programs using distance education technologies. The level of awareness of virtual technologies will increase significantly.

In educational activities, the tasks of distance education centers are to organize course activities for improving the qualifications of pedagogical staff in two directions: information and communication technologies and training of pedagogical staff by subject [2]. For users who have

just started in the field of virtual technologies, courses are held on the formation of computer skills, as well as on the use of virtual technologies in the professional activities of teachers.

In the field of subject preparation for teachers, distance courses related to the issues of teaching general education subjects are organized, and in the educational process, using Internet resources, the subject-oriented training of teachers and the organizers and participants of distance courses educational consultation is conducted between.

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